

ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SELECTED MEDICINAL PLANTS USING EURO ELEMENTAL ANALYSER

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ABSTRACT

Different elemental constituents at trace levels of plants play an effective role in the herbal formulation preparation. Elemental composition of different parts including leaves, seeds and fruits have been determined by using EuroEA Elemental analyser (EEA). The 4 elements of Nitrogen, Carbon, Hydrogen and Sulphur have been measured. Their concentrations were found to vary in different samples. Medicinal properties of these plant samples and their elemental distribution have been correlated.

Key words: Elemental analysis, *Desmodium triflorum*, *Allmonia nodiflora*, *Digeria muricata*, Chromatogram.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal drugs are being used as remedies for various diseases across the world from ancient times. In recent years, increasing interest has been focus on phytomedicines as safer and more conjenial of the human body. Medicinal plants come into preparation of various drugs singly or in combination or even or used as the principle source as raw material for the other medicines

[1] More than 40 elements have been considered essential to life system for the survival of both mammals and plants. An element is considered essential when reduction of its exposure below

a certain limit result consistently in a reduction in a physiologically important function or when the element is an integral part of an organic structure performing a vital function in that organism [2]. Two main criteria are considered when elements are said to be essential. The first one is absence from diet results in departures from normal growth and metabolism, and development of pathological symptoms, while the second is that pathological symptoms can be relieved by replacing the element. To be pharmacologically effective or essential, the trace element may need to be combining or chelated with some ligand, in order to be physiologically absorbed to prevent or cure impairment caused by deficiency of the element [3]. Active constituent of medicinal plants are metabolic products of plant cells and a number of trace elements play an important role in the metabolism [4]. The screening of the actual bioactive elements of plant origin and assessment of elemental composition of the widely used medicinal plants is highly essential. In present study an attempt was made to determine what essential elements are present and their levels in medicinal plants by using EuroEA Elemental analyser. The present study was aimed to explore the *Desmodium triflorum*, *Allmania nodiflora* and *Digeria muricata* plants leaves are evaluating the Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three medicinal plants including; *Desmonium triflorum*, *Digeria muricata*, *Allmania nodiflora* were analysed in the form of leaves. Plants material was collected freshly from the field. All plants material was first cleaned dried and then powdered using a electric blender. Samples (0.5g) were submitted as solution in 2% HNO₃ and high purity HNO₃ (TraceMetal Grade) and MilliQ water (18 MΩ) used for the preparation of the 2% HNO₃ stock solution. Samples digested with high purity HNO₃ (TraceMetal Grade) and HCl in aqua regia was used. After digestion, samples were diluted to 2% HNO₃. Total dissolved solid content in each sample must not exceed

0.1 wt % (e.g. 0.1 g per 100 ml of solution). There must be no suspended solids else filter with a 0.2 μ m cellulose nitrate syringe filter. Minimum sample volume have submitted in 5 ml. Optimal sample volume is between 7-10 ml. Then these digested samples were transferred in 50 ml by adding distilled water in them. Then filter the extract with filter paper (Whatmann No.42) and filtrate were collected in labelled plastic bottles. The solutions were analysed for the elements of interest utilizing EuroEA Elemental Analyser. The percentages of different elements in these samples were determined by the corresponding standard callibration curves obtained by using standard AR grade solutions of the elements i.e. Nitrogen, Carbon, Hydrogen and Sulphur.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plants analyzed in the present work with their botanical name, local name, part of the plant used, medicinal uses (Table 1). The results of elemental analysis obtained by comparator method of EEA are shown (Table 2, 3 and 4) in mg/g dry weight of the samples. It is to be noted that each result is an average of at least three independent measurements with a precision of about $\pm 1\%$. The data obtained from figure 1, 2 and 3. The results showed that *Allmania nodiflora* exhibits the percentage of the elements and Carbon (34.46), Hydrogen (5.041) and Nitrogen (1.90) (Table 2 and Figure 1). The Table 3 and Figure 2 showed tha *Desmodium triflorum* exhibits the percentage of the elements and Carbon (30.36), Hydrogen (4.97) and Nitrogen (2.08). The Table 4 and Figure 3 showed that *Digeria Muricata* exhibits the percentage of the elements and Carbon (23.39), Hydrogen (4.50) and Nitrogen (1.32). Highest contain carbon will generate energy required for the microbial metabolic activity. Compounds such as carbohydrates, in addition to being sources of carbon for the microbial biomass. Hydrogen used in the formation of amino acids, proteins, and oils. It is necessary for chlorophyll formation, promotes nodulation in legumes, helps develop and activate certain enzymes and vitamins, and is a structural component

of two of the 21 amino acids that form protein. Nitrogen is so vital because it is a major component of chlorophyll, the compound by which plants use sunlight energy to produce sugars from water and carbon dioxide (i.e., photosynthesis). It is also a major component of amino acids, the building blocks of proteins. Without proteins, plants wither and die. Nitrogen is an essential nutrient for the production of amino acids, proteins, nucleic acids, etc., and stone fruit trees require an adequate annual supply for proper growth and productivity. Nitrogen is primarily absorbed through fine roots as either ammonium or nitrate [5]. The active constituents of medicinal plant or the metabolic products of plant cells wherein a number of trace elements play an important metabolic role can be used medicinally for their therapeutic effect [6]. In addition the plants are used as the principal source of raw materials in the preparation of drugs. The presence of high element concentrations in the plants under study gives a new insight into their potential use to compensate for element deficiencies in man and animals as well as medicinal plants. The toxicity levels for the elements under study were within the safety baseline level for both man and animals [7]. The presence and concentrations of various elements in different plant depend on the composition of the soil, water and fertilizers used as well as permissibility, selectivity and absorbability of plants for the uptake of these elements. Hence, the observed variations in concentration of the elements are attributed to the nature of the plant as well as its surroundings [8].

Conclusion

The data obtained in the present work will be useful in synthesis of new herbal drugs with various combinations of plants, which can be used in the treatment of different diseases at global level generally.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Authors have no conflict of interest to declare

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TABLES

Table-1: Botanical names and uses of selected medicinal plants.

S.No	Species name	Family	English name	Local name	Part used	Medicinal uses
1	<i>Allmania nodiflora</i> (L)	Amaranthaceae	Node flower Allmania	Hasiru budde soppu	Stem, Leaves, Roots	Constipation, dysentery, antioxidant, antiinflammatory, anti-microbial
2	<i>Desmonium triflorum</i> (L.)	Fabaceae	Creeping Tick Trefoil	Kaadu pullampurasi	Roots, Leaves , Whole plant	Dysentery, diarrhoea, rheumatism, fever, stomach aches, indigestion, skin problems, wound and ulcers
3	<i>Digeria muricata</i> (L)	Amaranthaceae	False Amaranth	Gorajepalle	Leaves, Roots, Shoots	Constipation, GIT disorders, diabetes, diuretic

Table-2: Elemental analysis of *Allmania nodiflora*

Element	RT (S)	Area	Area %	Element %	Intercept	Slope	Correlation
Nitrogen	37	15,141	2.071	1.901	-0.004	5.332940 E-07	0.997639
Carbon	59	4,82,053	65.950	34.467	-0.020	1.949809 E-07	0.998369
Hydrogen	154	2,33,741	31.978	5.041	-0.004	6.226011 E-08	0.995817
Sulphur	-	-	-	-	-0.006	4.562577E-07	0.997605

Table-3: Elemental analysis of *Desmodium triflorum*

Element	RT (S)	Area	Area %	Element %	Intercept	Slope	Correlation
Nitrogen	37	34,618	1.890	2.086	-0.004	5.332940 E-07	0.997639
Carbon	59	1,182,925	64.566	30.363	-0.020	1.949809 E-07	0.998369
Hydrogen	153	6,14,577	33.545	4.978	-0.004	6.226011 E-08	0.995817
Sulphur	-	-	-	-	-0.006	4.562577 E-07	0.997605

Table-4: Elemental analysis of *Digeria muricata*

Element	RT (S)	Area	Area %	Element %	Intercept	Slope	Correlation
Nitrogen	37	15,775	1.923	1.323	-0.004	5.332940 E-07	0.997639
Carbon	60	5,03,307	61.344	23.395	-0.020	1.949809 E-07	0.998369
Hydrogen	154	3,01,389	36.734	4.504	-0.004	6.226011 E-08	0.995817
Sulphur	-	-	-	-	-0.006	4.562577 E-07	0.997605

FIGURES

Instrument Parameters

Carrier (kPa)	Purge (ml/min)	Oxygen (ml)	Delta P O ₂ (kPa)	Sampling Delay (s)	Run Time (s)	Front (°C)	Rear (°C)	Oven (°C)
110	80	15	35	5	360	980	Off	100

Chromatogram

Figure 1 – Elemental analysis of *Allmania Nodiflora*

Figure 2 – Elemental analysis of *Desmodium triflorum*

Figure 3 – Elemental analysis of *Digeria muricata*